

Inclusion complex formation of omeprazole with hydroxypropyl cyclodextrins

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Abstract : The effects of hydroxypropyl- α -cyclodextrin (HP- α -CD) and hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (HP- β -CD) on the twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT) emission of omeprazole (OMP) in aqueous solution were investigated by absorption and steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence techniques. The shorter wavelength (SW) band originates from the locally excited state and the longer wavelength (LW) band is due to the emission from a TICT state. The excited state fluorescence decay life time for the TICT emission was increased at higher CD concentration, whereas no significant change observed in the lower CD concentrations. The absorption and fluorescence spectral shifts and the size of the OMP suggest that OMP forms 1 : 1 inclusion complex at lower CD concentrations whereas 1 : 2 inclusion complex at higher CD concentrations. Semiempirical quantum optimization were also been carried out to assign the encapsulation of the OMP.

Keywords : Omeprazole, solvents, cyclodextrin, TICT, inclusion complex, PM3.

Introduction

The key property of cyclodextrins (CDs) is their ability to form complexes with a great variety of organic substances in solution and in the solid state. The physico-chemical properties of the included substances are altered upon complexation and CDs are widely used for enhancement of aqueous solubility, stability and bioavailability of nonpolar drugs¹. Chemically, CDs are cyclic oligosaccharides containing at least 6 D-(+) glucopyranose units, attached by α -(1,4) glucosidic bonds. The three natural CDs, α -, β - and γ -CDs, with 6, 7 or 8 glucose units, respectively, differ in their ring size and solubility^{2,3}. The cavity size of α -CD is insufficient for many drugs and β -CD is expensive. In the early stages, β -CD has been widely used of pharmaceutical applications because of its availability and cavity size suitable for the widest range of drugs⁴. However, its anomalous low aqueous solubility is a serious barrier in its wider utilization⁵. Since native CDs have low solubility in aqueous solvents, derivatives have been made by chemical modifications of the hydroxyl groups which greatly improve their solubility and their ability to dissolve hydrophobic compounds, as well as reducing their toxicity⁶.

Omeprazole ((*RS*)-6-methoxy-2-((4-methoxy-3,5-dimethylpyridin-2-yl)methylsulfinyl)-1*H*-

benzo[*d*]imidazole) is an anti-acid drug with a widespread use in the treatment of gastric hyperacidity related diseases, such as ulcer, therapeutic, esophagitis and gastro-esophageal reflux^{7,8}. Omeprazole (OMP, Scheme 1) inhibits the proton pump present in gastric mucosa cells, thus reducing acid secretion. OMP was evaluated for

Scheme 1

potential anti-inflammatory activity, with positive results⁹. The drug may protect gastric mucosa cells from inflammation, whether it is caused by *H. pylori* infection or by long-term administration of aspirin or other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs with harmful secondary effects on the stomach. In this way, OMP will bring a double therapeutic action in gastric hyperacidity disorders, reducing not only acid secretion but also the tissue inflammation caused by aggressive agents. Other studies investigated the mechanism of action of OMP, finding that it forms a covalent bond with the membrane proton pump. This type of enzyme also exists in yeasts, being vital to

their metabolism¹⁰. OMP can, therefore, be used as a fungicide, featuring activity against the yeast *Candida albicans*¹¹ the most common pathogen in fungal infections of the mucosae.

OMP is a weak base and is stable under alkaline conditions. The main pharmaceutical drawbacks are related to the physicochemical instability to heat, light, and acidic media. Moreover, the low aqueous solubility of OMP is responsible for low dissolution rates and hence low bioavailability¹². One way to overcome these problems is the complexation of OMP with CDs such as α -CD, β -CD or γ -CD. This is an established procedure to improve the biopharmaceutical properties of drugs with poor water solubility¹³⁻¹⁵. In the past few years, our research group has been focused on the study of some fluorescent drug molecules in various environments¹⁶⁻²³. So far, we have probed successfully the mean structural properties of solvents, pH and CDs. In the present work, we have carried out a comparative study of the interaction of HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD with OMP. The inclusion complex formed has been characterized in the absorption, steady state and time resolved emission techniques have been performed to investigate possible host-guest inclusion geometries.

Materials and methods :

OMP, HP- α -CD, HP- β -CD and spectrograde solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich chemical company and used without further purification. Triply distilled water used for the preparation of aqueous solutions. Aqueous solutions of pH below 2.0 and above 11.5 were prepared by adding appropriate amounts of dilute ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M) solutions of NaOH and H₃PO₄. All the spectral measurements were performed at the solute concentration of 2×10^{-5} M. The concentration of HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD solution was varied from 1×10^{-3} to 10×10^{-3} M.

Absorption spectral measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu UV 1601 PC model UV-Visible spectrophotometer and steady-state emission measurements were made by using a Shimadzu spectrofluorimeter model RF-5301. The emission lifetime measurements were performed using a picoseconds laser and single photon counting setup from Jobin-Vyon IBH (Madras University, Chennai). A diode pumped Millennia CW laser (Spectra Analysis) 532 nm was used to pump the Ti-Sapphire rod in Tsunami picosecond mode locked laser system (Spectra physics Model No. 4690 M3S). The Ti-Sapphire rod

is oriented at Brewster's angle to the laser beam. The wavelength tuning range was 280–540 nm, i.e. standard pico configuration. The emission decay of the sample was analysed using IBH data analysis software.

Results and discussion

Effect of HP- α - and HP- β -cyclodextrins :

Table 1 and Fig. 1 depict the absorption maxima of OMP at various concentrations of HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD. The absorbance of the OMP decreases with increasing concentration of both CDs (inset Fig. 1). The increased or decreased absorbance of drugs in the presence of CD is due to the formation of inclusion complexes¹⁶⁻²³. In the absorption spectra, no clear isosbestic point was observed in both CDs. It has been well known that, guest molecules can be incorporated into the CD cavity depending upon their size, geometry and hydrophobicity. The small absorbance change of the OMP in HP- α -CD is probably due to smaller cavity size and therefore, lack of complexation. On the other hand, the cavity size of HP- β -CD appears to be too wide to form a stable inclusion complex with the compounds when oriented axially in the CD cavity. The higher encapsulation of the OMP in HP- β -CD as compared to HP- α -CD may be due to the strong hydrogen bonding interactions of the tertiary nitrogen atom of the OMP ring with the alcoholic OH on the CD.

The emission spectra of the OMP were measured in aqueous solution in the presence of HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD and the spectra were displayed in Fig. 2. The emission maxima of OMP in water consist of a strong emission around 340 to 355 nm, which is mainly due to the locally excited (LE) state and a weak band around 455 nm corresponding to the TICT state. The emission spectrum of OMP in water excited at 300 nm (absorption maxima) consists of two broad bands with the maximum of 340–355 nm (shorter wavelength, SW) and a longer wavelength at 455 nm. With on increasing the CD concentrations, the normal emissions were blue shifted whereas slight red shifts were noticed in the TICT emissions. In both CDs, the emission intensities of OMP decreased at lower concentrations while increased at higher CD concentrations (insert Fig. 2); i.e. after addition of 0.002 M HP- α -CD or HP- β -CD to the aqueous solution, the SW band emission intensity markedly decreased and the maximum shifted slightly to blue. In the presence of

Table 1. Absorption, fluorescence maxima (nm) and life times of omeprazole at different concentrations of HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD

Concentration of CDs	HP- α -CD				HP- β -CD			
	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	τ	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	τ
0 (without CDs)	300	4.12	452	0.17	300	4.24	452	0.17
	276s	3.81	355	0.22	276s	3.96	355	0.22
0.002	300	3.99	457	0.21	300	4.11	456	0.21
	276s	3.78	340	0.26	276s	3.89	340	0.26
0.004	300	3.95	457	0.23	300	4.06	456	0.23
	276s	3.73	340	0.26	276s	3.82	340	0.26
0.006	300	3.84	457	0.28	300	4.02	456	0.29
	276s	3.70	340	0.26	276s	3.77	340	0.28
0.008	300	3.81	457	0.32	300	3.95	456	0.33
	276s	3.68	340	0.28	276s	3.73	340	0.29
0.010	300	3.78	457	0.32	300	3.88	456	0.33
	276s	3.62	340	0.31	276s	3.71	340	0.31
Curve fitting method :								
Binding constant (M ⁻¹)								
1 : 1	405		623		427		696	
1 : 2	13471		15542		14818		16352	
Benesi-Hildebrand method :								
1 : 1	226		309		257		389	
1 : 2	11432		14623		13214		17336	
Curve fitting method :								
ΔG (-ve) kJ/mol								
1 : 1	15.12		16.20		15.25		16.48	
1 : 2	23.95		24.31		24.19		24.44	
Benesi-Hildebrand method :								
1 : 1	13.92		14.44		13.97		16.48	
1 : 2	23.53		24.15		23.90		24.58	

lower CD concentrations, the emission intensity greatly decreased and the structure of the band is lost whereas it is increased at higher CD concentrations. The above results suggest that OMP formed different inclusion complexes with both CD solutions.

In the absence of CD solution, the typical dual emission of TICT can be seen even though the emission quantum yield of the normal emission around 350 nm and the TICT one around 455 nm is extremely low. The weak TICT emission has been presumably ascribed to the stabilization of the highly polar TICT state by strong dipole-dipole interaction with water and consequent rapid non-radiative transition to the ground and/or low-lying triplet state²⁴. The emission intensity ratio of the normal and TICT band I_a/I_b were changed when the concentration of HP- α -CD or HP- β -CD increases. Further, upon addition

of HP- β -CD to the aqueous solution of OMP, the TICT emission band is rather strongly enhanced than HP- α -CD. However, in both CD, the normal emissions also follow the similar trend. As the concentration of HP- α -CD or HP- β -CD increases, the I_a/I_b ratio of both normal and TICT emissions significantly varied. It can be seen as further evidence for the formation of mixer of inclusion complexes that the initial changes of the I_a/I_b ratios level off at high HP- α -CD or HP- β -CD concentration. The different spectral changes in the CD solutions suggest that the structural geometry of the OMP/CD inclusion complex at lower CD concentration is different from that of the higher CD concentration. In other words, it seems to be obvious that the inclusion behavior of OMP is considerably affected by the CD concentrations.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of OMP in different HP- α - and HP- β -CD concentrations (M): (1) 0, (2) 0.001, (3) 0.002, (4) 0.004, (5) 0.006, (6) 0.008 and (7) 0.01. Inset: Absorbance vs α - and HP- β -CD concentrations.

In both CD solutions, no clear isosbestic point was observed in the absorption spectra and thus one can rule out the possibility of the formation of a well-defined 1 : 1 complex. But based on our earlier results of various molecules¹⁶⁻²³, it cannot eliminate completely the possibility that the 1 : 1 inclusion complex. However, the spectral shifts of the OMP in HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD solutions are different from each other indicates different kinds of inclusion complexes exist in this system. In this case, formation of three different types of inclusion complex between OMP and HP- α -CD or HP- β -CD are possible i.e. (i) benzimidazole ring captured, (ii) pyridine ring present in the CD cavity and (iii) 1 : 2 (OMP : CD) inclusion complex formed. Considering the shape and dimensions of both CD, OMP can not completely encapsulate with the CD cavity. Since the length of OMP (15.89 Å) is higher than that of CD height (7.8 Å), in the 1 : 1 inclusion complex, either benzimidazole or pyridine ring present in the CD cavity, whereas in 1 : 2 inclusion complex, both the benzimidazole or pyridine rings are present in the two CD cavities.

Fig. 2. Emission spectra of OMP in different HP- α - and HP- β -CD concentrations (M): (1) 0, (2) 0.001, (3) 0.002, (4) 0.004, (5) 0.006, (6) 0.008, (7) 0.01. Inset: Emission intensity vs α - and HP- β -CD concentrations.

In the 1 : 1 inclusion complexes, both benzimidazole and pyridine ring encapsulated in the CD cavity while in 1 : 2 inclusion complex, the benzimidazole moiety have embedded in one CD cavity and the pyridine embedded in another CD cavity. At low and high CD concentration, OMP is bound to one and two CD molecules, respectively; this could explain the different interactions of absorption/emission spectra observed for the CD solutions. The large blue and red shifts observed for the LE and TICT indicates that, benzimidazole and pyridine ring forms strong hydrogen bonds, most likely to an oxygen and hydrogen of the CD respectively. This analysis reflects the formation of a mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 inclusion complexes with OMP : 2CD.

Stoichiometry of the inclusion complexes :

In order to determine the stoichiometry of the inclusion complexes, a Job's method²⁵ for the absorption/emission were applied keeping the sum of initial concentration of OMP and CD constant and the molar ratio of CD changing from 0 to 1. The absorption/emission intensity

of OMP in the absence of (I_0) and presence of CD (I) were determined respectively. A plot of $(A - A_0)/A_0$ and $(I - I_0)/I_0$ versus the molar fraction of CD was provided in Fig. 3. It shows that in OMP, the $(A - A_0)/A_0$ and $(I - I_0)/I_0$ values versus molar fraction gives the linear line, indicating a mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the OMP with CD in the inclusion complex.

Fig. 3. Plot of $(A - A_0)/A_0$ and $(I - I_0)/I_0$ versus mole fraction of CD; Job's plot using (a) absorption and (b) emission intensity : Total concentration was 4×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹. Molar fraction is given by $[CD]/[CD + OMP]$.

In general for a 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the OMP-CD inclusion complexes, one can describe the equilibrium as follows :

Here, OMP-CD and OMP-(CD)₂ represents the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 inclusion complex respectively and K_1K_2 are the equilibrium constants for the complex formation, when the concentration of OMP is assumed to be negligibly small relative to that of CD, the concentrations of the OMP in the mixed solution can be expressed as follows :

$$[OMP] = \frac{[OMP]_0}{(1 + K_1[CD]_0 + K_1K_2[CD]_0 [CD]_0)} \quad (3)$$

$$[OMP-CD] = \frac{K_1[OMP]_0 [CD]_0}{(1 + K_1[CD]_0 + K_1K_2[CD]_0 [CD]_0)} \quad (4)$$

$$[OMP-(CD)_2] = \frac{K_1K_2[OMP]_0 [CD]_0 [CD]_0}{(1 + K_1[CD]_0 + K_1K_2[CD]_0 [CD]_0)} \quad (5)$$

where $[OMP]_0$ and $[\beta-CD]_0$ are the initial concentrations. If the intensities of the emission originated from OMP-(CD)₂ can be obtained from the spectral data and the change of absorbance as increasing the CD concentration can be calibrated, the equilibrium constants may be calculated using the above eq. (5). The K is obtained for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are given in Table 1. The quantitative comparison of binding constants²⁴ of the two complexes suggests that HP- β -CD provides a better site to accommodate of deep inclusion of OMP than that of HP- α -CD. The corresponding formation constant (K) can be expressed as the following according to the law of mass action :

$$K = [OMP - (CD)_2]/[OMP][CD]^2 \quad (6)$$

where $[OMP-(CD)_2]$, $[OMP]$ and $[CD]$ are the concentration of the respective guests. The initial concentration of OMP and CD are respectively represented by the following equations :

$$[2OMP]_0 = 1 + K[CD]^2 [OMP] \quad (7)$$

$$[CD]_0 = 1 + 2K[CD] [OMP] [CD] \quad (8)$$

To indicate the degree of association between CD and OMP, it would be useful to introduce the degree of reaction, α , is defined as the ratio between the free OMP concentration $[OMP]_0$ to the total concentration of the OMP, $[OMP]$. Taking into account that (i) the variations in absorption and emission maxima is proportional to the OMP concentration and (ii) the CD is in a large excess with respect to OMP and at high CD concentration essentially all OMP molecules are complexed, α is shown to be depend on the initial concentration of CD, $[CD]_0$ as follows :

$$\alpha/1 - \alpha = 1/K[CD]_0^2 \quad (9)$$

The measured absorbance/emission intensity values (I) are directly related to α ,

$$\alpha = [\text{OMP}]/[\text{OMP}]_0 = I_\infty - I/I_\infty - I_0 \quad (10)$$

where I is the observed absorbance/emission intensity of OMP, actually measured at a defined OMP concentration, I_0 is the absorbance/emission intensity of OMP in absence of CD and I_∞ is the absorbance/emission intensity when the OMP is completely complexed by both CDs.

It is apparent from eq. (9) that the response parameter (α) has a certainly functional relationship with the concentration of CD and the inclusion constant (K). Eq. (9) provides the basis for the determination of K value. The experimental data were fitted to eq. (10) by adjusting K value (Table 1). The fitted result for the inclusion complex of CD with OMP is shown in Fig. 4. Four curves are calculated (two absorption curves, two emission curves) with eq. (9) with the different stoichiometric ratio. The formation constants obtained from the absorbance and emission intensity are considerably different from each other again supported the formation for two different complexes between OMP and CD solutions.

Fig. 4. The response parameter (α) as a function of $\log [\text{CD}]$. The curve fitting for experimental data were calculated from eq. (10).

From Table 1 one can see that the binding constant for OMP/HP- β -CD larger than that of the OMP/HP- α -CD complex because the orientation of OMP in the HP- α -CD inclusion complex is the different. The binding constants (K) values indicate that the OMP : HP- β -CD inclusion complex is more stable than OMP : HP- α -CD, which can be explained by HP- β -CD having the optimized size for its internal cavity (6.5 Å) to encapsulate the guest molecule. The formation constants are very sensitive to change of CD concentration further supported the different inclusion complex is associated with OMP.

The stoichiometry of the complexes of the OMP with the CD is also studied by using a modification of the well known Benesi-Hildebrand method (Fig. 5). The Benesi-Hildebrand^{26,27} plots deviate from linearity at higher con-

Fig. 5. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the complexation of OMP with α - and HP- β -CD : (a) Plot of $1/\Delta A$ vs $1/[\text{HP-}\beta\text{-CD}]$. Inset : Plot of $1/\Delta A$ vs $1/[\text{HP-}\beta\text{-CD}]^2$, (b) plot of $1/(I - I_0)$ vs $1/[\text{HP-}\beta\text{-CD}]$. Inset : Plot of $1/(I - I_0)$ vs $1/[\text{HP-}\beta\text{-CD}]^2$.

centrations of the hosts, indicating the formation of one OMP : 2CD complexes, as has been observed earlier with FVB¹⁷ and 2ABA molecule²³. The linear portions at

lower concentrations of CDs have been fitted to a straight line, in order to calculate the binding constant for the 1 : 1 complexes. The value of this binding constant obtained for HP- β -CD, is higher to that of HP- α -CD. With HP- β -CD, the binding constant of the 1 : 1 complex is found to be markedly higher than that with HP- α -CD. In order to ascertain the binding constants and the emission quantum yields of the 1 : 2 complexes with the CDs, the plot of the emission quantum yield ($1/\phi_f$) against the CD concentration, has been fitted to the equation :

$$\Phi_f = (\phi_0 + \phi_1 + K_1[CD] + \phi_2 + K_2[CD]^2) / (1 + K_1[CD] + K_2[CD]^2)$$

where ϕ_0 , ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the emission quantum yields of the free OMP, 1 : 1 complex and 1 : 2 complex, respectively²⁸. The values of ϕ_0 and K_1 from Benesi-Hildebrand analysis are used as constants in the equation. The binding constants and the quantum yields are then calculated by iterative non-linear least squares regression (Fig. 6, Table 1). The emission quantum yield (ϕ_f) is found to be significantly higher in the 1 : 2 complexes with CD than

Fig. 6. Plot of emission quantum yield (Φ_f) of OMP against the concentration of CDs : (a) Plot of Φ_f vs $[CD]$, (b) $1/\Phi_f$ vs $1/[CD]$.

in 1 : 1 complexes. The ϕ_f in the 1 : 1 complex with CD turns out to be comparable to that in its 1 : 2 complex with CD. This is an important pointer towards the cause of emission enhancement of OMP in the complexes. If the major reason for enhancement is shielding from water, then similar extents of enhancement should have been observed in the two kinds of 1 : 2 complexes. The major reason for the greater emission enhancement in the 1 : 2 inclusion complexes with CD is the more restrictive microenvironment in this complex, which is expected to hinder the flexing motion of the OMP. This issue is explained further using the time resolved emission studies.

Excited state life time :

To examine the CD-induced changes in the emission spectra of OMP, we measured the emission decay of the normal (350 nm) and TICT emission (455 nm) in aqueous solutions containing different concentrations of HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD. Fig. 7 depicts the typical TICT emission decay profiles in the presence of HP- α -CD and

Fig. 7. Fluorescence decay curve of OMP in water, 0.01 M HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD solution.

HP- β -CD. Their analysis together with the normal emission decays is listed in Table 1. The normal emission decay in the absence of CD exhibits a slight slow decay (0.22 ns) as a major decay component with a small contribution of fast decay component (0.17 ns). This decay behavior indicates the existence of the two different normal emitting species which compete with the conformational relaxation times required for the TICT state. It is noteworthy that the decay time of the slow component is similar to that of TICT emission within experimental uncertainty. This indicates that the equilibrium between the

locally excited (LE) state and the TICT state is achieved in water in a rather short period. However, in the presence of CD, the equilibrium between the LE and TICT states is modified by the formation of the CD inclusion complexes. The decay time of the fast component slightly increased at lower HP- α -CD/HP- β -CD concentrations, in contrast it is increased significantly at higher CD concentrations. The decay time of the TICT component increases significantly from water to HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD concentration. The relative quantum yield of the TICT component is increased upon addition of CD, while it is little changed at lower CD concentrations.

The decay time of the TICT emission was observed to be very short in aqueous solution and also influenced by addition of HP- α -CD or HP- β -CD. No rise component was observed in the TICT emission in the aqueous solution. This behavior indicates the competing process between the conformational relaxation required for the TICT state and the fast decay process of the normal emission. At lower HP- α -CD or HP- β -CD concentrations, the SW emission decay profile is weak triexponential decay without significant enhancement of the lifetime and the relative quantum yield. On the contrary, at higher CD concentrations, the TICT emission (0.33 ns) increased, suggesting the formation of different OMP/HP- α -CD and OMP/HP- β -CD inclusion complexes. The relative emission quantum yields and their lifetimes only slightly increased at lower CD concentrations. This is also consistent with little enhancement of the TICT emission in the CD solutions (Fig. 2). One note that a rise time of the TICT emission, which is different from the fast decay time of the normal emission, were increased as the CD concentrations increased, whereas it was very small at lower CD concentrations. This reflects that the TICT dynamics of the OMP at lower CD concentration is quite different from that of the higher CD concentrations^{29,30}.

The fast decay time of the normal emission corresponds to the rise of the TICT emission, and it is faster than the diffusion-controlled reaction time. On the other hand, considering that the lifetime of the slow process increases upon addition of CD to water, this slow process probably reflects the existence of excited OMP without water molecule in its neighbor or proper arrangement of water molecules for TICT to occur. This slow relaxational process is mainly due to a long-range polarization inter-

action to further stabilize the TICT state. It is to be mentioned that these two processes are similarly affected by both CDs; the relative quantum yield of the fast process decreases significantly, while that of the slow process increases at higher CD in contrast to little change in the quantum yield in the lower CD concentrations.

The CD dependent triexponential decay times of the normal emission lead us to conclude that both the forward and reverse TICT rates in the aqueous solution undergo a change in the presence of CD. Thus, the above results conform the formation of the TICT state becomes more favorable in the HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD solution than in the water. The CD dependences of the TICT dynamics may be interpreted on the basis of different interactions induced by forming different patterns of CD inclusion complexes. Since the fast process is due to the excitation of the ground-state complex between OMP and water through hydrogen bonding, the different CD dependences of the relative quantum yields of the fast and slow relaxational processes imply that the hydrogen-bonding interaction between OMP and water molecules in the presence of lower CD is different from that in the higher CD concentrations. In other words, both the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 inclusion complexes are formed with CD, but the encapsulation of both moieties (benzimidazole and pyridine ring) can be different with regard to facing CD cavity by forming different patterns of CD inclusion complexes depending on the kind of CD cavities.

Molecular modeling :

This is further supported by using semi empirical quantum mechanical calculations. The internal diameter of the HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD is approximately 5.6 and 6.5 Å and the height is 7.8 Å respectively. The diameter of the OMP is about 15.84 Å, which is much bigger than that of the HP- α - and HP- β -CD cavity. Therefore, either the benzimidazole or pyridine ring of OMP can be entrapped in to the HP- α -CD or HP- β -CD cavity as shown in Fig. 8. This should be the reason why the absorption and emission maxima for OMP in the presence of CD shows as different results as compared with that in the absence of CD. On the basis of the different orientations of OMP in α - and HP- β -CDs, it is clear that the increase in the relative life time of the fast component of the normal emission upon addition of CD is due to the formation of 1 : 2 inclusion complex. The negative ΔG values suggest

H4-H14 = 15.84	H4-H17 = 15.84	C14-C16 = 14.51	C14-C15 = 14.68
H14-H8 = 7.25	H8-H17 = 6.63	C8-C16 = 5.61	C8-C15 = 5.75
H14-C8 = 6.53	H14-S = 7.68	H14-H17 = 3.60	H17-H11 = 6.13
H14-H19 = 6.25	H19-H12 = 5.89	H19-H11 = 5.81	C16-C9 = 4.43
C15-C9 = 4.26	H6-H1 = 5.06	H4-H6 = 4.45	H4-H1 = 4.70
H4-C5 = 5.00	H4-N2 = 6.36	H4-C7 = 7.09	

Fig. 8. The energy minimized structure and bond length of OMP at PM3 level.

that formation of all the inclusion complexes is a spontaneous process.

Due to the presence of one methoxy and two methyl groups in the pyridine ring, this moiety becomes larger size relative to the HP- α -CD cavity may be also responsible for the formation of different types of inclusion com-

plexes than that of HP- β -CD. As shown in Fig. 9, one of the two different inclusion complexes would be the type I complex, in which the benzimidazole ring is located near the exit of the hydrophobic cavity, and the other would be the type II complex, in which pyridine ring is deeply located in the cavity. In HP- α -CD, the type I complex is more favorable than type II because of the large size of the pyridine moiety. In this case the pyridine group does not fit well to the rim of HP- α -CD. However, since the diameter of the HP- β -CD cavity is large compared to HP- α -CD, both the benzimidazole or pyridine ring locates in a much less polar environment in the HP- β -CD cavity; hence both the type I and type II complex can be formed in HP- β -CD. Supporting this, the TICT intensity of OMP is little increased with HP- α -CD concentration, whereas that of HP- β -CD, which effectively increased. Further, the absence of an isosbestic point seems to the formation of a mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes.

Table 2 and Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 presents the selected bond distances, bond angles and the most interesting dihedral angles of the OMP before and after complexation in HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD obtained from PM3 calcula-

Table 2. Geometrical parameters of OMP before and after inclusion in Hp- α - and HP- β -CD for the most stable inclusion complexes

Properties	OMP	OMP : HP- α -CD		OMP : HP- β -CD		
		Type-I	Type-II	Type-I	Type-II	
Bond length (Å) :						
H4-H14	15.84	15.90	16.01	16.54	16.07	
H4-S	8.86	8.98	8.99	8.83	8.84	
C14-C8	9.16	9.09	9.11	9.20	9.20	
C14-C15	14.60	14.48	14.43	14.33	13.91	
3HCO-HO (1°)		2.99		2.70		
SO-HO (2°)		2.56		2.48		
NH-O (glycosidic linkage)		2.56		2.95		
=N-HO (2°)			4.33	2.51		
N-HO (2°)					2.77	
Dihedral angle (°) :						
N1-C7-S	126	126	128	127	125	
C7-S-O2	102	102	103	102	102	
C8-S-O2	104	103	107	102	103	
N3-C9-C8	115	115	116	115	115	
Bond angle (°) :						
N1-C7-S-O2	16.47	8.01	0.73	2.11	20.69	
C7-S-C8-C9	169.37	162.46	-101	-15.43	143.75	
N3-C9-C8-S	-81.86	-79.61	-82	-85.85	-73.29	
C9-C8-S-O2	-85.08	-92.36	5.61	-98.81	-110.60	

Fig. 9. The energy minimized structures of (a) OMP : HP- α -CD type-I, (b) OMP : HP- α -CD type-II, (c) OMP : HP- β -CD type-I and (d) OMP : HP- β -CD type-II inclusion complex at PM3 level.

tions from the most stable structure. It was evident that in CD, the geometry of the OMP was slightly altered. The alterations were significant in dihedral angles, which indicated that the drugs adopted a specific conformation to form a stable complex. Fig. 8 and Table 2 shows the intermolecular hydrogen bonding distance between the

above groups with CD oxygens of the glucosidic bridges are less than 3.0 Å conformed OMP should bind to the oxygens of the glucosidic bridges, as such an interaction is observed for structure. Further, the optimized theoretical structure of the OMP : CD inclusion complexes (1 : 1) confirmed the OMP is partially included in the CD cavity.

Conclusions :

The following conclusions can be drawn from the solvent study : (i) Dual emission is observed in OMP in aqueous and CD solutions. A normal Stokes shifted band is assigned to the locally excited $^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ or LE state and the large Stokes shifted band originates from the TICT state, (ii) OMP forms mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 inclusion complexes, (iii) the ratio of the TICT emission to the normal emission of OMP increases as the CD concentration increases, (iv) the HP- β -CD dependences of the TICT and normal emission decay of HP- α -CD is quite different from the HP- β -CD dependences. These results are explained in terms of different complexation patterns between the CD and the guests, (v) theoretical studies suggest that the guest is favored to enter into the cavity of the CDs from the wide side rather than the narrow side and (vi) analysis of the thermodynamic data indicates that the stoichiometries of all the CD inclusion complexes is driven by enthalpy process.

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